

NEW LOCALITY DATA FOR THE ORB-WEB SPIDER *ARANEUS COCCINELLA* POCOCK, 1898 FROM SOUTH AFRICA (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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Abstract: *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898 is a South African endemic described from a female collected in Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Prior to this paper, the species was only known from the type specimen. It is a rare spider and is now known from a few localities in Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal and Limpopo in South Africa. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *A. coccinella* based on images of living spiders, and provide information on its behaviour and distribution.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

Data on *Araneus* species diversity in South Africa is limited and outdated. According to the World Spider Catalog (2020), 13 *Araneus* species are known from South Africa, all of which were described between 1898 and 1950. In a recent publication by Nentwig *et al.* (2020), five of these species were listed as *nomina dubia*. The only recent paper on South African *Araneus* was the transfer of *Larinia vara* Kauri, 1950 to *Araneus* (Marusik 2017).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The identification of the araneids is a problem, as most of the genera have not been revised. As part of SANSa, a Virtual Museum database was developed to provide access to the photographs submitted by the public for identification (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). For the first time, images of living specimens of the coccinella spider, *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898, were available. *Araneus coccinella* is a South African endemic that was described from Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal, and could be positively identified based on Pocock's (1898) description.

The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *A. coccinella* based on images of living spiders, their behaviour and distribution.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Araneus coccinella spiders were sampled during SANSa and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

TAXONOMY

Araneus coccinella Pocock, 1898

Araneus coccinella Pocock, 1898: 211, pl. 8, fig. 6 (Df).

Type: Holotype female from South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal, Estcourt (-29.01, 29.87), deposited in British Museum of Natural History (not examined).

Diagnostic characters: Female: Size: total length 6 mm. *Araneus coccinella* can easily be recognised by their body shape and spotted abdomen (Fig. 1). Carapace varies from cream with dark patches in thoracic region in younger specimens (Fig. 2) to black in older females (Fig. 4); cephalic region slightly elevated, bearing numerous white setae; in older specimens the white hairs are restricted to the cephalic region; carapace slightly longer than wide (Fig. 1). Female palp yellow-orange. Eyes in two rows; anterior eye row recurved; posterior eye row almost straight (viewed from above); median eyes widely separated from lateral eyes; eyes small, all same size. Sternum dark, heart-shaped. Legs short, with coxae and trochanters black, remaining leg segments orange-yellow, with black bands on distal ends of all of the metatarsi and tarsi. Abdomen oval, longer than wide; anterior portion rounded, posterior rounded and projecting slightly beyond the spinnerets; orange-yellow above, decorated with eight black oval spots, arranged in two parallel lines (Figs 1-2); in some specimens the anterior spots merge (Fig. 4). Venter entirely black (Fig. 3). Epigynum: with short triangular scape (Figs 5a-b), deeply excavated above, ending posteriorly in a rounded apex. Male unknown.

Figure 1. *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898 female from Soutpansberg, dorsal view (Photo: Peter Webb).

Figures 2-4. *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898. (2) Female from Irene, dorsal view; (3) Female from Irene, lateral view; (4) Female from Wakefield Farm, dorsal view, showing the variation in abdominal markings (Photos: P. Webb).

Figures 5-6. (5) Ventral epigyne of *Araneus coccinella* from Soutpansberg (Photo: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman); (6) Original line drawing of female epigyne by Pocock (1898).

Habitat: The species was sampled with a sweepnet from grassland. In Irene, Gauteng, a small grassland patch was regularly sampled over a period of ten years. Specimens of *A. coccinella* were regularly found during the summer months (November to February) and were sampled in 2011, 2014-2016 and 2019. In the Limpopo Province, it was sampled during altitudinal transect surveys in the Western Soutpansberg.

Global distribution: South Africa. New records: South Africa (Gauteng, Limpopo) (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. South African records of *Araneus coccinella*.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Gauteng: Irene veld (opposite Gem Village) (-25.87, 28.23), leg. P. Webb, 2.xi.2011, 1f (NCA 2011/385); Same locality, 4.ii.2014, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2015/3314); Same locality, 20.xii.2015, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/551); Same locality, 10.1.2016, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/552). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Wakefield Farm, near Howick (-29.50, 29.89), 23.xi.2015, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/553).

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